

Design and Experimental Study of a Multichannel Instrument for ESP32-Based Digital Acquisition and Local Monitoring of Biological Parameters of the Baby's Body

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a multichannel instrument for simultaneous digital acquisition and local monitoring of three biological parameters of a baby's body, i.e., ECG (ElectroCardiGram) signal, temperature and humidity. The integrated hardware modules of proposed the instrument consist of an AD8232 device for ECG detection, a DHT11 sensor for both temperature and humidity detection, and an ESP32 WROOM microchip for digital signal acquisition. A virtual prototyping of the instrument is built using Fritzing software, while Arduino IDE/C++ is used for real time programming of automated instrumentation tasks. The monitoring target of the whole digital measurement is a virtual USB monitor embedded into Arduino IDE-C++, which is initially set up at 9600 bd. The experimental results obtained from a well tested workbench show the realistic nature and the high quality of the proposed multichannel instruments for biological parameters of a baby. Compared to existing biological instruments for babies, its novelty relies on numerous factors including higher number of input channels, lower overall size, lower building cost and more flexible for further extension to Android/wireless monitoring terminals.

Key words: Multichannel instrument, biological parameters, baby's body, Arduino IDE/C++, ESP32 WROOM

INTRODUCTION

A human's body is well known as a complex biological machine. Under given operating conditions, it involves a wide variety of biophysical signals, each of which being described by specific time varying waveforms. Most popular examples of biophysical signals encountered in biomedical instrumentation literature are recalled as follows in biomedical engineering literature ([1], [2], [3]): ECG (ElectroCardiGram) from a heart, temperature of a leaving body, neighbourhood skin humidity, EMG (ElectroMyoGram) from muscles; EEG (ElectroEncephaloGram) from a brain, ENG (ElectroNeuroGram) from nerves, ERG (ElectroRetinoGram) from the retina of an eye, EOG (ElectroOculoGram) from the cornea/retina of an eye, MEG (MagnetoEncephaloGram) from the magnetic field of a heart, USG (UltraSonoGram) from a foetus in a mother's womb, etc.

The biomedical instrumentation engineering has been and remains a relevant attractive field for scientific research opportunities. Beside numerous existing biomedical instrumentation systems, many open problems remained unsolved, e.g.: a) Most bio-instruments encountered are single channel devices [1-6], hence acquiring multiple biological waveforms on a single patient requires distinct instruments, and the whole measurement process is uncomfortable and inefficient; b) A few existing multichannel biomedical instruments [7], might involve greedy investment for possible extension to a Wifi monitoring Terminal; c) Except some papers such as in [8], there is a great lack of research works on biomedical instruments for babies as recommended in [9]. These aforementioned weaknesses arising from the biomedical instrumentation literature, are major motivating reasons of this paper.

The pioneering biomedical instrument initiated in this paper is a multichannel instrument for simultaneous measurements and monitoring of baby's body parameters, i.e., ECG signal, temperature and humidity.

BUILDING TOOLS, METHODS AND EXPERIMENTATION

The schematic diagram of the proposed multichannel instrument is presented in Fig. 1. It consists of 04 main parts numbered from 1 to 6 respectively.

Fig. 1 Schematic diagram of the proposed multichannel digital biomedical instrument

Building hardware and specific software tools

The building hardware tools of the schematic diagram presented in Fig. 1 consist of a few hardware devices and specialized free software tools. Fig. 2 summarises these building hardware modules, e.g.: 1) 03 ECG probes and associated EGC cables with coloured connectors (red, yellow and green); 2) AD8232 ECG conditioning board, offering optimum performances (low noise, common mode rejection, high gain) within 0.5-40 Hz frequency bandwidth (see [10] for details technical details); 3) DHT11 module with build-in temperature sensor for 0-50 °C range, and humidity sensors with 20-80 range (see [11] for more technical details); 4) PC/Laptop with preinstalled specific software tools to be listed later; 5) ESP32 WROOM microchip from Espressif;

Fig. 2 Main building hardware modules

It is worth noting here that DHT11 sensor offers a single digital serial pin for both the temperature and humidity output data. As shown in Fig. 3, a digital output word stream structure is organized into 40 serial bits [11]. Therefore, a direct computing from low level programming of temperature and humidity values for acquired serial bit streams might be highly tedious. Fortunately, DUT11 library yielding low level automated subroutines are used in practice to overcome the difficulty as it will be outlined later.

Fig. 3 Bits stream structure of DHT11 sensor output data [11]

It is worth noting also that ESP32 WROOM microchip family offers numerous build-in instrumentation capabilities including [12]: a) dual 32 bits core, reconfigurable multipurpose pins (DIO, DAC, ADC, PWM, I²S and I²C instrumentation bus); b) PCB antenna, Wifi (802.11, 2.2-2.5 GHz, access point or client mode or both); c) Bluetooth (BLE, 4.2 version); d) ready to use on-board Hall sensors; e) capacity touchelectrodes; f) up to 32 MB flash memory; g) enable and reset buttons; h) 3.2 V power supply and more. For these relevant technical reasons, ESP32 microchip family has increasingly becomes the most attractive choice for ambitious and innovative instrumentation projects as in [12], [13], [14],[15] and [16].

On the other hand, the specific software tools required for design or real time programming tasks are described in Table 1.

Table -1 Specialized software tools

Specific software tools	Version	Technical relevance
Fritzing	0.9.3b	Virtual prototyping of the instrument
Arduino IDE	1.8.12	C++ sketch programming
Arduino DHT11 sensor Library	1.4.2.zip or Adafruit version 1.1.4	To be installed into Arduino IDE/C++
ESP32 WROOM driver for Windows	CP210x_Universal_Windows10_Driver.zip	To be installed into Windows 10
ESP32 WROOM library for Arduino	https://dl.espressif.com/dl/package_esp32_index.json	To be installed from Arduino IDE
AD8232 library for Fritzing	Heart_Rate_Monitor_demo.fzz	To be installed into Frotwing

Methods

The relevant need at this methodological subsection is to show how the virtual prototyping model of the proposed biomedical instrument has been implement and in both virtual and real worlds.

The resulting virtual instrument model build in Fritzing software platform is depicted on Fig. 4, where all hardware modules are mounted on a virtual electronic board.

Fig. 4 Virtual prototyping model of the proposed biomedical instrument under Fritzing

In the next step, the second relevant need is to outline the flowchart from which the automated instrumentation tasks might be coded at programming time as a set of C++ sketch to be compiled into Arduino IDE/C++ framework. A brief list of instrumentation tasks to be automated via programming for further real time processing by ESP32 WROOM are:

- Digital acquisition of input temperature and humidity from corresponding DHT11 ADC pins;
- digital acquisition of ECG samples from corresponding AD8232 ADC pins;
- Digital signal processing (DSP) of sampled signals according to target goal;
- Monitoring of DSP results on virtual Arduino IDE monitor via USB data transfer process at 9600 bd.

It is worth noting that the related DSP process subroutines take into account physical constraints and numerical analysis needs associated with each input channel. Fig. 5 show the main flowchart associated with the aforementioned instrumentation tasks to be further implemented as a source C++ sketch.

Fig. 5 Flowchart of the ESP32-based automated instrumentation tasks

The set of first steps {a, b, c} are heading tasks associated with external libraries, data types dictionary and hardware setup respectively. Then, the remaining sequential steps {d, e, ..., i} are periodic tasks according to a digital processing loop logic, with time period T (ms). In digital signal processing practise, a suitable value of T is dictated by Nyquist's sampling frequency [17], which is at least 2 times the maximum frequency required to process all tasks and delays involved within the loop. However, an occurrence of a reset signal initializes of the whole digital-based automated system.

A second relevant information to be outlined in depth in Fig. 5 is the numerical computing policy of ECG samples given digital values acquired from AD8232 output pins. In this paper, the computing algorithm used is organized into 5 steps as follows:

- 1) A threshold is fixed for a digital R wave sample;
- 2) The R wave is detected on the basis of the time index for which the acquired is greater to the given threshold level;
- 3) The digital gap between time indices values are computed (R-R interval).
- 4) A mean of last sixteen interval R-R is computed.
- 5) The heart rate frequency is determined according to relationship (1).

$$\text{Heart_Rate} = \frac{60000}{\text{AVG}(\text{R} - \text{R interval})} \quad (1)$$

where AVG stands for the average operator.

Fig. 6 shows the main heading section of C++ sketch as viewed under Arduino IDE/C++ platform.

```

#include <dht11.h>
#define DHT11PIN 4

dht11 DHT11;
float temperature = 0 , humidite = 0 ;

#define PI 3.141592
unsigned int temps=0;
unsigned int Minute=0;
unsigned int entree=0;
unsigned int entreen1=0;
unsigned int entreen2=0;

float filtre;
float filtren1;
float filtren2;
float derivation;
float derivation1;
float derivation2;
float derivationABS;

unsigned int centi;
unsigned int centiST;
float ST; //seconde
unsigned int periode;

bool flag=0;
bool flag1=0;
bool flag2=0;

unsigned int BPM;
unsigned int average;
const int numReadings = 120;
int readings [numReadings];
int readIndex = 0;
long total = 60;

float a1=1;
float a2=1;
float detectionfiltre;
float detectionfiltren1;
float pentedetection;
float sortie;
float sortie1;
float sortie2;

void setup() {
// initialize the serial communication:
Serial.begin(9600);
pinMode(10, INPUT); // Setup for leads off detection LO +
pinMode(11, INPUT); // Setup for leads off detection LO -
}

```

Fig. 6 Heading section of the C++ sketch under Arduino IDE/C++ platform

Experimental Research

At this study step, the set of Figures from Fig. 1 to Fig. 5, appears to be a sufficient technical knowledge base, from which a complete experimental workbench can be surely designed and built in order to prove the realistic feasibility and good quality of the proposed multichannel biomedical instrument for babies. The image sample of the resulting experimental workbench is presented in Fig. 7.

The complete isolated workbench shown in Fig. 7a, is a real world realization of the Frizing-based virtual instrumentation system earlier presented in Fig. 4. It is worth noting that all the building hardware modules depicted earlier in Fig. 2 are quite visible, including real wires for signal transmission among parts. On the other hand, Fig. 7b shows an experimental session where the ECG electrodes are appropriately connected to a 05 month old baby's. Then a few minutes are sufficient to automatically complete a biomedical data acquisition session.

Fig. 9 shows an experimental sample of a baby's ECG on the screen of the Virtual USB Arduino monitor. It is a great challenge to see that, under a permanent agitation of baby's body, the crude ECG waveform provided by the proposed instrument is quite satisfactory. However, the quality might be improved using a low-pass digital filter.

CONCLUSION

The multichannel biomedical instrument initiated in this paper relies on innovative building technology. Design studies and experimental results obtained on a well tested workbench have proved that, it offers higher flexibility, lower size, and better suitability for baby's needs, compared to existing biological instrumentation systems. However, a few technical improvements remain necessary, e.g., noise level reduction on crude ECG samples using an appropriate digital low pass filter, replacing Arduino virtual monitor by a local LCD with possible extension to Android terminal via IoT (Internet of Things) networks. This notorious improvements will be conducted in our future research works.

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